

Table S1. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	1
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	2-3
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	4
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	4
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	4
Information sources*	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	4-5
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	5
Selection of sources of evidence†	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	5-6
Data charting process‡	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	6

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	6
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence§	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	6
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	6
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	6
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	7-10
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	7-10
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	7-10
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	10-24
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	25-29
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	30
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	29-30
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	31

Table S2. PCC Model.

Criteria	Determinant
Population/ phenomenon	Perishable food supply chain management
Concept/Intervention	Perishable food access
Context	Remote Indigenous communities across global regions

Table S3. Eligibility criteria for screening

Criteria	Include	Exclude
General source information		
Type	Published and unpublished studies and grey literature	-
Year	1996-2024	Before 1996
Language	English	Other languages
Study type	All study types, including case studies, abstracts, text and opinion papers, commentaries, and editorials	Study protocols
Study design	Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods	-
Remote Indigenous communities		
Country	All high-, middle-, and low-income countries	-
Geography	All	-
Population	Remote Indigenous population, diverse study populations that include Indigenous Peoples	General population
Perishable food supply chain management		
Food type	Perishable market-sold foods	Traditional foods that are not sold in markets and do not involve monetary transactions. Non-food products such as cigarettes
Study focus	Food supply, food access	Studies assessing health, diet, and food security that do not explicitly link them to PFSCM will be excluded from the analysis. Public health initiatives that do not expressly consider PFSC interventions will be excluded.

Table S4. Literature search keywords

Context	Keywords	Combinations
Countries with remote Indigenous communities	Australia, Brunei Darussalam, Canada, Chile, Finland, French Polynesia, Greenland, Guam, Israel, Japan, New Caledonia, New Zealand Northern Mariana Islands, Norway, Palau, Panama, Sweden, Taiwan, United States, Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, Peru, India, Kenya, Ethiopia, Madagascar, Uganda.	Australi* OR "Brunei Darussalam" OR Canad* OR Chile* OR Finland OR Finnish OR "French Polynesia*" OR Greenland* OR Guam* OR Israel OR Japan* OR "New Caledonia*" OR "New Zealand*" OR "Northern Mariana Island*" OR Norw* OR Palau* OR Panam* OR Swede* OR Taiwan* OR "United States" OR American OR Argentina* OR Brazil* OR Colombia* OR Mexico* OR Peru* OR India* OR Kenya* OR Ethiopia* OR Madagascar* OR Uganda
Indigenous Peoples	Aboriginal, Autochthonous, First People, Indigenous, Native, Melanesian, Pacific Islanders (Pasifika, Pacific people), Polynesian, Tribal, Remote areas, Remote*,	Aboriginal* OR Autocht* OR "First people" OR Indigenous OR Native* OR Melanesian OR "Pacific Islander*" OR Pasifika OR "Pacific people" OR Melanesian* OR Polynesian* OR Trib* OR "remote areas" OR remote*
Australia	Australian Aboriginal, Torres Strait Islander	"Australian Aboriginal*" OR "Aboriginal Australian*" OR "Torres Strait Islander"
Brunei Darussalam	Belait, Bisaya, Brunei, Dusun, Kedayan, Murut, Tutong, Iban, Penan	Belait OR Bisaya OR Brunei OR Dusun OR Kedayan OR Murut OR Tutong OR Iban OR Penan
Canada	First Nation, Inuit, Métis	First Nation* OR Inuit OR Métis
Chile	Atacameño, Aymara, Colla (Kolla, Qulla), Diaguita, Mapuche, Quechua, Qawasqar (Kawesqar, Kawaskar, Kawesqár, Alacalufe), Rapanui (Rapa Nui), Yámana, Yagán, Yagan, Yahgan	Atacameño OR Aymara OR Colla OR Kolla OR Qulla OR Diaguita OR Mapuche OR Quechua OR Qawasqar OR Kawesqar OR Kawaskar OR Kawesqár OR Alacalufe OR Rapanui OR "Rapa Nui" OR Yámana OR Yagán OR Yagan OR Yahgan
Finland, Norway, Sweden	Sami (Saami)	Sami OR Saami OR Sapmi
French Polynesia	French Polynesian, Polynesian*, Marquesan*	"French Polynesia*" OR Marquesan*
Greenland	Inuit, Greenlanders	Inuit OR Greenland*
Guam	Chamorros	Chamarro* OR Guam
Israel	Bedouin (Bedu)	Bedouin OR Bedu
Japan	Ainu (Aynu)	Ainu OR Aynu
New Caledonia	Kanak	Kanak* OR "New Caledonia"
New Zealand	Māori	Māori
Northern Mariana Islands	Chamorros	Chamarro* OR "Northern Mariana Islands"
Palau	Palauan	Palau*

Panama	Bribri, Bokota, Emberá, Guna (Kuna), Naso (Terribe), Ngäbe-Buglé (Guaymi), Wounaan	Bribri OR Bokota OR Emberá OR Guna OR Kuna OR Naso OR Terribe OR Ngäbe-Buglé OR Guaymi OR Wounaan OR "Comarca indígenas" OR comarca*
Taiwan	Amis, Atayal, Bunun, Hla'alua, Kanakaravu, Kavalan, Paiwan, Puyuma, Rukai, Saisiyat, Sakizaya, Seediq, Thao, Truku (Taroko), Tsou, Yami (Tao)	Amis OR Atayal OR Bunun OR Hla'alua OR Kanakaravu OR Kavalan OR Paiwan OR Puyuma OR Rukai OR Saisiyat OR Sakizaya OR Seediq OR Thao OR Truku OR Taroko OR Tsou OR Yami OR Tao
United States	Alaska Natives, Native Americans (American Indians), Native Hawai'ians (Kanaka Maoli)	"Alaska* Native*" OR "Native American*" OR "American Indian*" OR "Native Hawai'ian*" OR "Kanaka Maoli"
Uruguay	Guaraní Mbyá, Charrúa	"Guaraní Mbyá" OR Charrúa
Argentina	Guaraní, Mbyá, Wichí, Mataco, Toba, Mapuche	Wichí OR Mataco OR Toba OR Mapuche
Brazil	Waiwai, Kayapó, Arará, Guarani	Waiwai OR Kayapó OR Arará OR Guarani
Colombia	Zenú, Palenqueros, Wayúu, Raizales, U'wa	Zenú OR Palenqueros OR Wayúu OR Raizales OR U'wa
Mexico	Yucatán, Mixes, Chiapas	Yucatán OR Mixes OR Chiapas
Peru	Shuar	Shuar
India	Boro, Bodo, Siddi	Boro OR Bodo OR Siddi
Kenya	Maasai	Maasai
Ethiopia	Oromo, Somalis	Oromo OR Somalis
Madagascar	Mauritius, Comoros	Mauritius OR Comoros
Uganda	Maragoli	Maragoli
Perishable food	Fresh, Fruit*, Perish*, Perishable*, Vegetable*, Vegies	Fresh OR Fruit* OR Perish* OR Perishable* OR Vegetable* OR Vegies
Food access	Adequacy, Affordability, Availability, Cost, Diet affordability, Diet cost, Food access*, Food price, Food supply, Food quality, Food security	Adequacy OR Affordability OR Availability OR Cost OR "Diet affordability" OR "Diet cost" OR "Food access*" OR "Food price" OR "Food supply" OR "Food quality" OR "Food security" OR "Food stability" OR food
Supply chain management	Cold chain*, Demand*, Demand chain*, Distribute*, Grocer*, Last mile*, Logistic*, Logistics*, Logistics network*, Manager*, Network*, Operation management*, Operations*, Owner*, Procurement*, Produce*, Purchase*, Retail*, Sale*, Store*, Supermarket*, Supply*, Supply chain*, Supply network*, Transport*, Vendor*	"Cold chain*" OR Demand* OR "Demand chain*" OR Distribute* OR Grocer* OR "Last mile*" OR Logistics* OR "Logistics network*" OR Manager* OR Network* OR "Operation management*" OR Operations* OR Owner* OR Procurement* OR Produce* OR Purchase* OR Retail* OR Sale* OR Store* OR Supermarket* OR Supply* OR "Supply chain*" OR "Supply network*" OR Transport* OR Vendor*

Table S5. Pilot database search results

Date	search strings	Database used	Number of publications retrieved
2024-11-18	<p>(TS=(Australi* OR "Brunei Darussalam" OR Canad* OR Chile* OR Finland* OR Finnish* OR Greenland* OR Guam* OR Israel* OR Japan* OR "New Zealand*" OR "Northern Mariana Island*" OR Norw* OR Palau* OR Panam* OR Swede* OR Taiwan* OR "United States" OR America* OR Argentina* OR Brazil* OR Colombia* OR Mexico* OR Peru* OR India* OR Kenya* OR Ethiopia* OR Madagascar* OR Uganda* OR communit*) AND TS=(Aboriginal* OR Autocht* OR "First people*" OR Indigenous OR Native* OR "Pacific Islander*" OR Pasifika OR "Pacific people*" OR Melanesian* OR Polynesian* OR Trib* OR OR remote*) OR TS=("Torres Strait Islander*" OR benoit OR biscayan OR Brunei OR Dusun OR kawasan OR murat OR tutong OR Iban OR penan OR "First Nation*" OR Inuit OR Métis OR Atacameño OR Aymara OR Colla OR Kolla OR quila OR diaguita OR Mapuche OR Quechua OR qadaskar OR kawesqar OR Kawesqár OR alacalufe OR Rapanui OR "Rapa Nui" OR Yámana OR Yagán OR yaman OR yahgan OR Sami OR Saami OR Sapmi OR "French Polynesia*" OR Marquesan* OR Inuit OR innuit OR inuk* Greenland* OR Chamarro* OR Guam OR Bedouin OR Ainu OR Kanak* OR "New Caledonia*" OR Māori OR Chamarro* OR "Northern Mariana Island*" OR Palau* OR bribery OR bogota OR Emberá OR Guna OR Kuna OR Naso OR Ngäbe-Buglé OR Guaymi OR wannana OR OR comarca* OR Amis OR Atayal OR bunin OR Hla'alua OR kanakanvu OR kalasin OR Paiwan OR puyuma OR rakai OR saisiyat OR sakizaya OR Thao OR turku OR tarokh OR Tsou OR Yami OR Tao OR "Alaska* Native*" OR "Native American*" OR "American Indian*" OR "Native Hawai'ian*" OR "Kanaka Maoli" OR "Guaraní Mbyá" OR Charrúa OR Wichi OR matano OR Toba OR Mapuche OR weihai OR Kayapó OR Arará OR Guarani OR Zenú OR palenquera OR Wayúu OR raizales OR "U'wa" OR Yucatán OR Mixes OR Chiapas OR Shuar OR Boro OR Bodo OR sidhi OR Maasai OR Oromo OR Somalis OR Mauritius OR Comoros OR marangoni OR Amerind*))</p> <p>AND</p> <p>(TS= ((Fresh OR Fruit* OR Perish* OR Vegetable* OR Veggies NEAR/3 ("Cold chain*" OR Demand* OR Distribut* OR Grocer* OR "Last mile*" OR Logistics* OR Manage* OR Network* OR Operation* OR Owner* OR Procurement* OR Produc* OR Purchas* OR Retail* OR Sale* OR Store* OR</p>	Web of Science	765

	<p>Supermarket* OR Supply* OR supplies OR Transport* OR Vendor* OR Manufactur* OR Consum* OR Legislat*))</p> <p>AND</p> <p>(TS= ((Food* OR diet* OR nutrition) NEAR/3 (adequacy OR affordab* OR availab* OR cost* OR access OR price* OR supply OR quality OR security OR stability OR deserts OR consumption OR problem* OR shortage* OR stocks)) OR (Fresh OR Fruit* OR Perish* OR Vegetable* OR Veggies) NEAR/2 (access OR price* OR affordab* or availab* OR quality OR supply)</p>		
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Table S6. Data extraction questionnaire.

Concept	Questions	Definitions
Q 1. Title		
Q 2. Year published		
Q 3. First Author (Last name, first initial)		
Q 4. First author's institutional affiliation type	Select one: Academic Government Private institution Other	
Q 5. Country and city of the lead author's institutional affiliation	List	
Study Characteristics		
Q7. What was the research design of this study?	Select one: Primary research study Review study (i.e., using systematic or scoping review methods) None	
Data Collection Methods		
Q8. What data collection methods did the study use?	Select one: Quantitative Qualitative Mixed qualitative and quantitative Other (specify) _____ Not applicable	
Geographic Location and Study Population		
Q 9. What country/countries are research conducted in?		
Q 10. Specify the regions where the study occurred		For example, Nunavut, Alaska
Q 11. Geography		As defined in the study, definitions of rurality and remoteness may differ between studies accordingly. For example, Island, Remote, Urban, Rural, Arctic, Northern, ...
Q 12. Which Indigenous peoples were relevant in this study, as identified by the article? (See Table 2)		

Supply chain		
Q 13. What supply chain actors are involved in the study?	Describe what the units of analysis are?	
Q 14. Does the paper identify specific PFSC management challenges that affect food access?	Select one: Yes No If yes, describe how	
Q 15. Were specific practices or solutions identified for addressing challenges?	Select one: Yes No If yes, describe	